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Sports Journalism: a case study in Professionalism
and Objectivity using Agenda Setting, Framing,
Priming and Gatekeeping theories

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Abstract

The rise of social media platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter, has had a significant impact on how news is reported, particularly online. It allows for direct communication between journalists and their audiences, which can lead to hidden agendas being present in news dissemination. This thesis is an analysis of how agenda setting, framing, priming, and gatekeeping affect the way football news is covered on social media. Additionally, it explores how these practices impact the objectivity and professionalism of the journalists in football news reporting.

A qualitative content analysis of social media posts related to two prominent football journalists across multiple platforms was conducted to gain a deeper understanding of the agendas that influence online football news reporting. Through this approach, it was possible to identify crucial patterns and trends in the coverage and presentation of online football news. The study shows that professionalism and objectivity are connected to how football news is presented online, through agenda setting, framing, priming, and gatekeeping. Football journalists use different frames to structure and select news, such as sharing their opinions and engaging with their audience using selected pictures, and repeating topics that may be influencing their audience's opinions on the subject.

It is concluded that football journalists heavily influence the audience's perception through the selection and the use of pictures and descriptions. The strategic implementation of framing approaches allows them to manipulate the narrative. Moreover, the frequency of coverage plays a critical role in shaping the audience's later opinion. The comment sections on social media platforms are sources for biased discussions that can further reinforce a skewed perspective. These phenomena have shown the operation and emergence of agenda

setting, framing, priming and gatekeeping within the social media context as well as the impact on the objectivity and professionalism of football journalists.

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Statement of Authorship

This thesis contains no material that has been submitted for examination in any other course or accepted for the award of any other degree or diploma in the university or other institution and, to the best of my knowledge and belief, contains no material published by another person except where due reference is made in the text.

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Supervisor statement

As Supervisor of Chan Choeh Jiat, I confirm that the work submitted in this dissertation has, to the best of my knowledge, been carried out by the student named above, and is worthy of examination.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

At a press conference, a football journalist asked Pep Guardiola, who is currently the coach of Manchester City and has previously coached Barcelona and Bayern Munich, whether he could lead a team to victory in the Champions League without star players like Messi, Xavi, and Iniesta. Guardiola agreed with the statement, possibly to prevent any potential tension that could arise if he gave a different answer (Lee, 2019). The journalist's intention may have been to generate controversial headlines if Guardiola had disagreed. The incident was thought-provoking and raised a controversial question about whether the football journalist acted professionally. To answer the question, it is necessary to understand the phenomena of professionalism, objectivity, and agenda setting in football journalism. This thesis is a case study of content shared by football journalists on social media and analysed using theories of framing, priming, and gatekeeping. The information I gathered comes from social media posts, tweets and accounts, which I refer to as "threads". I use these conversations and information as examples to demonstrate the theory and agenda-setting framing being used.

1.1 Significance

The significance of this research lies in its relevance to sports journalism and journalism in general. It highlights the two crucial codes of ethics, which are "proactive" and "restraining", that journalists need to abide by while reporting the news. The proactive code empowers journalists to report the news freely, but without any biases or preferences, and by seeking and presenting the truth. The restraining code, on the other hand, emphasises the accountability of journalists towards the public while reporting the news (Ward, 2019). In essence, the primary objective is to provide factual and trustworthy information to the public.

Therefore, it involves objectivity and professionalism. In journalism, objectivity refers to reporting events without any personal opinions or biases. This ensures that the news accurately reflects the truth and reality of the situation (Wein, 2005, p. 4). In ethical journalism, the accuracy and fairness of news is important. Professionalism is necessary to provide reliable and comprehensive information without any speculation or inaccuracies (Ibbi, 2016). According to agenda setting theory, it influences and directs our thoughts towards certain topics (Baran, 2009, as cited in Salman et al., 2016). It is noted that journalists have the ability to highlight certain aspects of the subjects they cover, which can be presented in a broad manner (Weaver, 2007) while, according to priming theory, people use the information that they already have in their memory when making a decision (Goidel et al., 1997). The thesis, also, provides a clear insight into the differences in approaches of the two journalists who are actively reporting news on social media, like Facebook, Instagram and Twitter.

This thesis includes five chapters. The first chapter serves as an introduction. In Chapter 2, the focus is on objectivity and professionalism in sports journalism. It also covers agenda setting, framing, and priming theories, as well as social media platforms and gatekeeping theory. This chapter sets the research question, compares the backgrounds of football journalists and provides information on related football clubs. Chapter 3 outlines the research methodology, consisting of a methodological approach, an understanding of the sampling of big data and a case study brief. The case study involves two football journalists, Matt Law and Fabrizio Romano. In Chapter 4, a detailed analysis is conducted on the ways in which two journalists interact with social media platforms and their respective audiences. This is to gain a deeper understanding of the underlying frames that are involved in these interactions, as well as the potential consequences. Furthermore, a comparative analysis is provided for the two journalists in order to highlight the key differences and similarities that have emerged,

while also shedding light on the frames that have been established. The fifth chapter is a conclusive chapter of the thesis and offers a concise and thorough discussion, providing a definitive end to the entire thesis. This section serves as a summation of the research and presents a thoughtful conclusion that ties together all of the previous findings.

Chapter 2:

Sports Journalism and Agenda Setting

In this chapter, I will provide an overview of sports journalism, agenda setting theory and introduce the two major sports journalists of interest to this thesis. I will also outline the research questions.

2.1 Objectivity and Professionalism in Sports Journalism

Sports Journalism is part of the Department of Journalism. How we judge and analyse if the news was professionally reported should also be the same. Hence, it also involves objectivity and professionalism in news reporting. Objectivity is defined as being executed in a way where journalists' personal opinions and assessments are distant from an event to keep the news' truth and reality (Wein, 2005, p. 4). It is described as the "cornerstone principle" in journalism (Muñoz-Torres, 2012). However, it is, sometimes, hard to distinguish objectivity and facts because journalists are first-hand witnesses of an event. It is up to them to be objective or subjective when reporting the news because facts do not speak for themselves (Wein, 2005, p. 5). Therefore, if the personal views of a journalist can be separated from the facts, it means that objectivity is applied. Unfortunately, in journalism nowadays, many war reporters have been told to report news afar from the battlefield, as it is safer. By the time the reporters reached the battlefield, the war would have finished, and they are not first-hand witnesses capable of producing news with true objectivity (Wein, 2005, p. 7).

In 2022, a Belgian international and Chelsea player who is currently on loan to Inter Milan, Romelu Lukaku, posted, "If you have to force it, then it probably doesn't fit" on Snapchat just a few weeks after a controversial interview with his club and the coach at that time, which many reporters interpreted on different sites that Lukaku was sending a message to the

club and the coach (O'Brien, 2022), even though no evidence has explicitly shown that the message was targeting the aforementioned. This is, undoubtedly, related to the objectivity and professionalism of a reporter. In Lukaku's case, if the reporters wanted to be objective without adding their own opinions, the title would have just been the incident itself without adding a line which indicates that he posted this message after the controversial interviews weeks before. The application of professionalism is needed to prevent inaccuracy and speculation of the message from happening because professionalism in ethical journalism is believed to secure the dissemination of accurate, fair and thorough information (Ibbi, 2016). However, what holds the application of professionalism back is the ownership and control of a country, the government's power, and the rich in society (Ibbi, 2016). Hence, journalists must opt between professionalism and survival (Ibbi, 2016), as a group or an organisation can utilise professionalism to reduce journalistic autonomy in favour of them (Merill, 1974, as cited in Singer, 2003).

Journalists have faced challenges in being objective. They are often expected to report news in a traditional and conservative manner, which can limit their writing style. This can sometimes prevent audiences from interpreting a subject for themselves (Ward, 2008). However, objectivity is crucial in leading the way to uncovering the truth about a topic (Cunningham, 2003). That is because, sometimes, when a journalist stays within the field by observing the situation for too long with objectivity, they tend to feel like it is their time to obligatorily speak out what they think, as much as the facts, after the evidence which they have been accumulating in that particular field (Cunningham, 2003). Besides that, professionalism is defined as a core element in journalism which helps to "provide clear, accurate, objective and ethical coverage of issues" (Shah et al., 2021, pp. 1). Therefore, it proves that objectivity is part of professionalism, as objectivity is linked with

professionalism. Therefore, if a journalist is not objective enough, they lose their professionalism in journalism, even though they feel, occasionally, that they have to speak their mind.

2.2 Agenda setting, Framing and Priming Theory

Agenda setting theory argues that news focuses our minds *on what to think about* instead of influencing our initial *way* of thinking (Baran, 2009, as cited in Salman et al., 2016). News is influential in shaping the direction of how audiences should think about a particular “important” topic (Salman et al., 2016). Social media has reduced the control of conventional media over news flows and indirectly made social media a platform to create and share news easily (Salman et al., 2016), as sharing news on social media can help the dissemination reach a larger audience group (Feezell, 2018). Feezell (2018) suggests that the intention of users on social media is to socialise and share personal information. This increases the likelihood that agenda setting exists on social media because the users do not have the intention to filter out, in their minds, what they want to read in an objective way. Journalists, consequently, can successfully utilise the social media platform to implement the agenda setting idea and disseminate it to the audiences on social media.

The aforementioned incident of Romelu Lukaku has something to do with agenda setting and framing theory, as these theories link to objectivity. To explain and analyse it, agenda setting originally meant the media’s portrayal towards an idea that draws the audience’s attention to its subjectivity, which has now been known as the “first level” of agenda setting (Coleman et al., 2009). The incident was reported to emphasise what Lukaku had posted because the public will think a professional sportsperson will normally focus more on training than social media. Therefore, people and other sports sites will pay more attention to this incident after

publishing the news. In other words, Coleman et al. (2009) suggest that “the first level agenda setting focuses on how much media coverage the topic receives” (p. 149), while the “second level” of agenda setting pays attention to the discussion of the topic. With more research being done on this topic, I noticed that a few other famous sports sites are also reporting this incident, such as Goal.com (Tolmich, 2022), Daily Mail (Cancian, 2022), and so on.

However, the media or journalists have added lines where it seems their personal opinions are involved in news reporting. This is seemingly a very suspicious act to frame sports news, as the news and topic, particularly in Daily Mail, created a controversial scenario by generally outlining a controversial interview of Lukaku with Chelsea Football Club to frame as if he posted the message publicly because of his apology of the interview and his unsatisfied opinion on the coach, Thomas Tuchel’s tactics.

Framing and priming, undoubtedly, play a vital role in the presentation of football news, as framing theory suggests, journalists draw the audiences’ attention to certain attributes of the objects of new coverage. Some perspectives can be very generally framed (Weaver, 2007), while priming theory points out that people rely on the information that is already stored in their memory at the time of the decision (Goidel et al., 1997). Besides that, below the Lukaku news, some audience commented, mostly negatively, below based on the news reported above, which can be explained as the result of priming. Therefore, if there were no intentions of setting an agenda for this incident, the journalist or media could have just objectively reported Lukaku’s sent message online, to let the audience decide upon themselves, without adding more information or intentionally creating speculation on what the message was trying to convey and who the targeted person was.

Objectivity, professionalism, agenda setting and framing, therefore, are related and linked in sports journalism, as there are only slight differences between them. Objectivity aims to show “both sides of the story” without “favouring one side over the other” (Raejimaekers, 2017). Professionalism is used to make sure accurate, fair, and thorough information is disseminated. On the other hand, agenda setting is executed to draw the public’s attention to an issue and then observe how much focus the topic receives, via the application of framing, as the second level agenda setting is believed to be an issue-specific frame (Entman, et al., 2009). Even though they appear to be slightly different from one another, they share the same goal, which is to disseminate a message or information on an event depending on the journalists’ and media’s preferences, as there are limitations that hold them back, such as opting between being professional or to survive, the ownership, control, and the power of an organisation.

2.3 Social Media Platforms and Gatekeeping Theory

The rise of social media plays a vital role in influencing sports journalism. Twitter is an obvious example to demonstrate its influence, albeit it has a 140-word limit in disseminating news (Schultz & Sheffer, 2010). Initially, Twitter was used for social networking, providing a platform for users to connect with friends, family, and others (Johnson, 2009, as cited in Schultz & Sheffer, 2010). However, it has emerged to be utilised by others to retrieve more information instead of only social networking (Kwak et al., 2010). In this new era, so-called “influencers” have emerged with the intention to create and spread content to Twitter users (Anger & Kittl, 2011). This proves that even though there are limited characters to write on a Twitter post, people still use it as a platform to disseminate messages or content. Hence, journalists use Twitter to spread breaking news to catch audiences’ attention with the help of Twitter’s news publishing speed (Schultz & Sheffer, 2010). One of the many famous football

journalists, Fabrizio Romano uses “HERE WE GO” as a sign of breaking news, to catch the audience’s attention even with Twitter’s 140-word limit (Romano, 2021), which attracted approximately 327.5K likes, 24K Quote Tweets and 67.4K Retweets. As a sports journalist, Romano interacts with football fans on Twitter (Romano, 2019). This is a huge emergence of social media, in disseminating sports news and getting the message across to the target audiences. Therefore, it has changed the way sports news is reported. However, Twitter also provides a platform for a big organisation like the International Association of Football Federation (FIFA) to frame the news in a subtle way. FIFA World Cup deleted a tweet that possibly trolled Cristiano Ronaldo after his country’s World Cup exit and his rival, Lionel Messi’s completion of a trophy set after winning the World Cup (HT Sports Desk, 2022). This shows that it indirectly frames Lionel Messi as better than Cristiano Ronaldo.

Another interesting media phenomenon is called gatekeeping. Gatekeeping is defined as the process of news selection, “writing, editing, positioning, scheduling, repeating, and otherwise massaging information” (Shoemaker et al., 2008, as cited in Tandoc, 2014). It involves news selection and presentation (Cassidy, 2006) with the process of going through several layers when the news was under construction (Shoemaker and Vos, 2009, as cited in Tandoc, 2014). Journalists on Twitter are considered gatekeepers because they retweet the news or messages that were posted on Twitter to their followers (Lasorsa et al., 2012, cited as in Russell, 2015). In this case, journalists are the gatekeepers who share information with their audiences about what they think should be disseminated after filters and determination because they decide what information should be spread (Cassidy, 2006).

Journalists do decide to seek headlines by asking controversial questions or unrelated questions to trap the interviewees so that audiences’ thoughts on one issue can be led to the direction in favour of the journalists. For example, before a UEFA Champions League match

started between Liverpool FC and Napoli FC, a journalist asked Liverpool's head coach, Jürgen Klopp, about Naples' safety, which is irrelevant to the football match whatsoever (Guardian Football, 2022). In this case, if the interviewee was trapped, audiences would start to think that Naples is a dangerous city instead of focusing solely on football. Another similar controversial interview was between a journalist and with ex-Chelsea coach, Thomas Tuchel (Guardian Football, 2022). Tuchel was asked about the Russo-Ukrainian War in a Chelsea football press conference, an event for journalists and football coaches to provide updates solely on football teams and matches, a devious way to divert the audience's attention away from the sport since Chelsea's ex-owner was a Russian billionaire and was under sanction. These are clear examples demonstrating that sports journalists frame and gatekeep news not only on social media, like Twitter, but also in press conferences. Sports journalists, therefore, can be said to be influential in sports news production because they play the roles of "reporters, correspondents, editors and producers" that gather and process information about others and, later on, transmit it to the audiences (Gans 1979: 80, as cited in D'Angelo & Shaw 2018). In other words, journalists are the ones who determine what news to report and in what directions they want to bring the audiences.

2.4 Research Questions:

My research and investigation of various social media sites and media on objectivity, professionalism, agenda setting, framing and gatekeeping, the research questions of my study would be narrowed down to:

RQ1) How do agenda setting, framing, priming and gatekeeping operate in football news within the context of social media?

RQ2) Are objectivity and professionalism in football affected by particular types of agenda-setting, framing, priming and gatekeeping?

In order to answer these research questions, I analyse two examples of football journalism on Twitter.

2.5 Football Journalists

Football journalist, Matt Law shares and provides updates on football news on Twitter. He often shares or retweets news on Twitter, adding his own opinion on it. He openly criticises Tottenham Hotspurs' player Richarlison after his poor performance lately, and his interview publicly complaining about the lack of game time on the pitch (Matt Law, 2023). He criticises Richarlison by retweeting Telegraph Football's tweet and adding his opinion letting the public know that Richarlison scored only one goal for Tottenham Hotspurs this season and is yet to score in English Premier League (EPL). This is to directly state that he has been performing poorly, and that is why he was not getting his playing time. In addition, he tweeted his opinion on why he thinks Richarlison was not selected in the starting line-up by directly saying, "he did the grand sum of nothing", which attracted the public to start interacting with him by commenting below, and most of their opinions are similar to Matt Law. While he shares his opinions on a topic on Twitter, the public start to interact with him by commenting, and most of their opinions are similar to Matt Law. A famous football journalist's opinion can be influential towards the audience. It shows that agenda setting is placed simultaneously, which leads the audience to a particular direction of what to think, which is to think that Richarlison is a terrible player with his recent form. In this case, the use of words is very essential in influencing the public's thoughts. Framing is involved in this

case, as the public was given information to decide which side they should take and support (Firdaus, 2004).

Another football journalist, Charlie Parker-Turner, provides updates about football news on Twitter, and he stated in his Twitter biography that he is a fan of Brighton & Hove Albion Football Club (BHA). He also shares his opinions on BHA Football Club-related news and sometimes defends the club, if he has to, when tweeting (Charlie Parker-Turner, 2023). For example, he replied, “I hope you laughed whilst typing”. It means that he is telling the public his opinion and he tells people what should think and defends his favourite football team. This can be called the **defence frame**, that he is framing the issue while defending his point of view on the football club. It, sometimes, will trigger the comment section where some football fans would start commenting no matter if they are with or against Parker-Turner. He, then, will fight back if he thinks he has to defend his club (Charlie Parker-Turner, 2023). This demonstrates that sports journalists can create a space with agenda setting, framing and priming theory involved. After all, in this case, it can be seen that Parker-Turner drew his audiences’ attention to the transfer of a Chelsea player, Conor Gallagher, adding his opinions on Chelsea’s hesitation in accepting this bid, too. His audience, then, will start discussing this particular topic of Chelsea’s action, which eventually was described by the audience as “greedy”. This can lead to priming theory, too, because, later on, the audiences might think that Chelsea is a greedy club once there is some news about Chelsea and the transfer windows. These examples show that football journalists are the ones who draw attention public’s attention to a subject, as it is explained that, if a person is mentioned by “@username” on Twitter, the more influential they are and the ones who drive the content (Chu & Fletcher, 2014). Therefore, the agenda is allowed to be set on Twitter to directly influence the audience (Yang et al., 2016, as cited in Wang, 2022).

Furthermore, Goal.com, a sports news and media company, Tweeted, “Antonio Conte didn’t hold back with his comments about Tottenham” (Goal.com, 2023) after Antonio Conte, the Tottenham Hotspurs head coach at that time, publicly criticised the mentality and the lack of enthusiasm of the club (The Guardian, 2023). In this case, the public’s attention was drawn to Tottenham Hotspurs’ negative football mentality, and it can lead the public to think that Tottenham Hotspurs are not doing well enough, and some even commented below saying that Conte purposely criticises the club because he wants to be sacked. It indirectly sets an agenda to tell people what direction to think of an issue.

2.6 Related football clubs’ backgrounds

There are several important football clubs that will be referred to in the thesis, and a brief description is provided of them.

Arsenal Football Club (AFC)

Arsenal FC is one of the most famous football clubs in England, with the achievement of being the only team to finish a league season with an unbeaten run in contemporary football. Their fanbase size is around 89.33 million as of 2023 (footgoal, 2023). Its nickname is “The Gunners” (Ambille, 2021). Its rivals are Chelsea FC and Tottenham Hotspur FC (Siregar, 2022). The revenue of the club is reported to be 367.1 million pounds as of 2021-22 (BBC, 2023).

Aston Villa Football Club (AVFC)

Aston Villa Football Club is a club based in Birmingham and was founded in 1874 (Aston Villa FC Official Club Website, n.d.). It is a popular and famous club in the Midlands of the

United Kingdom with a fanbase of 10.99 million fans as of 2023 (footgoal, 2023). Its nickname is “the Villans” (Ambille, 2021).

Chelsea Football Club (CFC)

Chelsea FC is a London-based football club founded in 1905 and is one of the five clubs to have won all three pre-1999 main European club competitions (Chelsea FC Official Site, 2021). It has accumulated a number of 127.5 million fans as of 2023 (footgoal, 2023).

Chelsea FC has rivalries with Tottenham Hotspur, Arsenal, West Ham United and Fulham (Siregar, 2022). Its nickname is “The Blues” (Ambille, 2021). The revenue of the club is around 481.3 million pounds as of 2021-2022 (BBC, 2023).

Tottenham Hotspur Football Club (THFC)

Tottenham Hotspur FC was founded in 1882, and its nickname is “Spurs” (Ambille, 2021).

The club has been mocked by fans online, knowing that their last major trophy won was only in 2008 (Mcevoy, 2018); (Official Spurs Website, n.d.). Their biggest rivals are Arsenal FC and Chelsea FC (Subham, 2023). Their revenue is reportedly shown to be 442.8 million pounds as of 2021-22 (BBC, 2023), while their fanbase is 72.38 million fanbase as of 2023 (footgoal, 2023).

2.7 Comparing Major Football Journalists

There are two major sports journalists of interest to this thesis, Matt Law and Fabrizio Romano. They were chosen because of their significant differences in the way they report and interact with their audiences.

Matt Law states on his Twitter biography that, he joined Twitter in 2010. He is an Aston Villa Football Club (AVFC) fan from his interview with Football Writers' Association (FWA) back in 2012, publicly admit that Villa Park, Aston Villa's Stadium, is among the best stadium while their rival, Birmingham City Football Club's stadium, St Andrews Stadium is obviously the worst (FWA, 2012). Law also tweeted on Twitter, saying that Villa Park is decent (Matt Law, 2022). Initially, for the first two years, he mostly tweeted and replied to others about his interest in funny videos, music videos and occasionally about Aston Villa Football Club and Arsenal Football Club. Since 2012, his exposure to other football clubs started to get wider, as he would start to add opinions on other football clubs' news by tagging related people or players (Matt Law, 2013). Later on, he started to mock Tottenham Hotspur by posting an edited meme picture on Twitter, adding his opinion on the management of Tottenham Hotspur Football Club (Matt Law, 2015). Besides that, Diego Costa, a former Chelsea Football Club player, publicly revealed that he was told by the Chelsea ex-coach, Antonio Conte, he was sent a message to let him know that he would no longer be in next season's plan. Based on this issue, Matt Law tweeted it adding his opinion saying Chelsea had made their situation more difficult and he did not understand the reason why Chelsea did this, which attract the audience's discussion in the particular tweet (Matt Law, 2017). In 2017, Matt Law also posted a tweet directly letting the audiences know his opinion on Liverpool Football Club's new signing, Virgil Van Dijk, saying that he does not think he is worth the price Liverpool paid (Matt Law, 2017). This tweet also attracted audiences who have different opinions on Liverpool, discussing below the tweet stating their opinions to criticise and agree with Matt Law or defending Liverpool and criticising Matt Law. Recently, in 2022s, he tweeted a lot about the managerial changes at Aston Villa. the latest news and injury news about Chelsea, Tottenham Hotspur, and other football clubs.

Fabrizio Romano, one of the world's most famous and most trusted football journalists, reports football news for Sky Sports Italy, mostly in a neutral way (Arora, 2020). He does not create speculations and only posts about football news that will 100% happen with his famous signature term, "Here We Go", to surely confirm that the event about a player or a football club will occur (Deodhar, 2021). For example, on 13th July 2022, Romano tweeted that former Leeds United player, Raphinha, would join the Spanish giant, FC Barcelona with the "Here We Go" term and some details on this transfer (Romano, 2022). On the same day, FC Barcelona and Raphinha co-posted a picture of Raphinha in Barcelona jersey on Instagram, officially declaring that Raphinha joined FC Barcelona (FC Barcelona, 2022). Furthermore, he tweets the latest updates of players, too, without adding any of his personal opinions. For example, Romano tweeted about Arsenal's defender, Takehiro Tomiyasu's injury condition and the plan for the rest of his season (Romano, 2023), as the club and the player himself confirmed, too (Arsenal FC, 2023); (Tomiyasu, 2023).

There are differences between Matt Law's and Fabrizio Romano's tweets on providing updates to the latest football news. On both ends, Matt Law and Fabrizio Romano would post a picture of a related person followed by a description with related information and recent updates of the particular person. However, on Matt Law's end, he will add his own opinions to the person he is giving updates on. For example, he added his opinions, saying that Chelsea's goalkeeper, Kepa Arrizabalaga is not the best goalkeeper Chelsea need in the long term (Matt Law, 2023). On the other hand, on Fabrizio Romano's end, he tells the public about the exact situation without adding his own opinions but with related information and emojis. For example, he says in a tweet that Chelsea's midfielder, N'Golo Kanté was back on the pitch after a long and serious injury as well as the discussion of Kanté's contract extension (Romano, 2023). Additionally, sometimes, he tweets about a player using true

statistics based on the particular player, as he did on Manchester City's striker, Erling Haaland, when he scores a lot of goals in just a few matches' time (Romano, 2023). In general, there is agenda-setting in both ways, namely "picture frame", because it can have effects on the public's later judgement and behaviour towards the players or the football clubs (Roskos-Ewoldsen et al., 2002).

In summary, in the chapter, I have provided an overview of sports journalism, agenda setting theory and two key sports journalists of interest to this thesis. With the rise of social media platforms, new ways of reporting news online emerge, especially on Twitter, as a major platform for users to consume news online. Thus, it is said that there were biases in online news reporting (Saez-Trumper et al., 2013). Gatekeeping plays a vital role in driving the professionalism and objectivity of a football journalist, which leads to the potential agenda setting, namely framing and priming, that may have to be placed because of personal or organisational demands. It needs to be carefully investigated, and it is possible to understand whether an agenda is set in a news report or production by collecting and analysing the existence of the different types of news on different online platforms, for example, Twitter, Instagram, and Facebook, reported by different football journalists.

Agenda setting theory is also a method, a way of analysing news content as well as theorising about it. In Chapter 3, I provide an overview of the case study approach used in the thesis.

Chapter 3

Research Methodology

As discussed in Chapter 2, agenda setting is both a theory and a method. I have chosen two high-profile sports journalists to study, using agenda setting analysis and within a case study methodology. In this chapter, I outline my case study approach.

“Methods” can be defined as tools for data collection, for example, questionnaires and observation, and they help in analysing the collected data, while “methodology” refers to the study of the applied methods (Bryman, 2008). In other words, “methods” are used for data generation, collection, and analysis (Miles, 2015), while “methodology” refers to the “ontological, epistemological, and axiological considerations” (Miles, 2015, p. 310) to attempt to understand the relationships of the target study groups and the theoretical concepts, namely framing and priming as methods.

A case study is a research methodology that helps to study intensively a group or a person via a qualitative or quantitative approach. After data collection, an in-depth understanding of the studied group or the studied person would be gained (Heale & Twycross, 2018). It is used to “explain, describe and explore” an event which can be done in a variety of ways, while this research focuses on an interpretivist approach that aims to try to understand the contexts perceived from different perspectives of the football journalists (Crowe et al., 2011, p. 4). Therefore, doing a case study can help to make sense of the particular football journalists’ opinions, intentions, and approaches towards the presentation of football news by taking into account hidden agendas like framing and priming.

Please note that this thesis is an exploratory case study with the aim of examining "What is happening?" The study offers new insights into the interactions between sports journalists and their audiences through social media, which was not previously possible on legacy media platforms. Through these interactions, frames may be built up. In the past, sports journalists had no direct contact with fans and could only communicate through mail and personal contact with fan clubs. This thesis provides valuable insights into the nature of sports journalist and audience interactions, and future studies could build upon these findings.

3.1 Methodological Approach

Qualitative research can be defined as a tool to help "describe and explain" the studied groups or "person's experience, behaviours, interactions and social contexts" without using statistics (Fossey et al., 2002, p. 717). In other words, one can use it to understand the interpretation of studied groups or a person's experience in a particular context (Merriam et al., 2019), while content analysis is defined as a systematic method to mainly analyse written messages in a particular content (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008). Therefore, qualitative content analysis was utilised in this research. In this research, qualitative content analysis was used to investigate, explore, and answer whether professionalism and objectivity in football journalism are still present during the rise of social media, for example, Twitter and Facebook, in relation to agenda-setting, namely framing and priming, as it is said that individuals' perceptions can be shaped by media (Scheufele et al., 2016). In other words, qualitative content analysis suggests understanding a phenomenon, instead of generalising results based on statistical inference of the study sample (Forman & Damschroder, 2007). In qualitative content analysis, the words and pictures were studied and analysed by selected football journalists to compare the style of posts, usage of languages and selection of pictures. This method was chosen because it focused on the texts that were already posted or tweeted

by football journalists. Therefore, it was useful to identify if professionalism and objectivity were present or if the agenda was already set, as it was not practical to interview the football journalists by asking them about their professionalism and objectivity in this field because analysing their posts will help answer the research questions.

To collect data in this research, a wide range of Twitter and Facebook posts and reactions, from 2017 to the present, posted and tweeted by several football journalists, for example, Matt Law and Fabrizio Romano, and the audiences were studied and, later on, analysed. This can help to understand better how football news and updates were posted, how the messages were conveyed and how the audiences interpreted the message and interacted with the football journalists or with one another. Therefore, the content and data found were secondary sources, as there was no interview of football journalists or anyone related conducted in this research. Thus, contents, like the usage of words and the selection of pictures, can be studied and analysed while taking framing and priming theories into account.

3.1.1 Sampling- Access to big data on Matt Law and Fabrizio Romano

I organised Facebook's full access to its databases, covering all posts in the English Language. Facebook runs its research access through CrowdTangle. My supervisor Dr Mark Balnaves assisted me in this. On CrowdTangle, users can search for specific posts using the search engine. They can apply filters such as platforms, account types, timeframe, and languages to refine their search. The search results will include related posts along with statistics on the amount of interaction related to the selected topics.

Through the access granted to me, I was able to compare the level of engagement on posts between Matt Law and Fabrizio Romano. I could also view individual posts easily. There

were 7 posts for Law and 19 for Romano, as outlined in Chapter 4. My selection process was to read all relevant posts across the period, all 200 of them. Frame analysis involves understanding similar words and sentences and their meaning in natural language. This involved understanding the meaning behind similar words and sentences in natural language, which was quite tedious. However, my analysis chapter highlights a sample of relevant posts that are indicative of the frames.

3.2 Case Study Research

This case study aims to answer the research question on the presence of professionalism and objectivity in football journalism during the rise of social media platforms, Twitter, and Facebook, in relation to agenda setting, framing, and priming. This is a qualitative content analytical case study where the sources are secondary, and the use of words and the selection of pictures were closely examined. Hence, it can be demonstrated if an agenda was set for the target audiences or if professionalism and objectivity are salient. Furthermore, the reached population of the research is large because they can be users of Facebook or Twitter who are following or not following the specified football journalists, as long as they are interested and want to get involved in football news updates. In addition, the degree of falsifiability is considered high because the existence of professionalism and objectivity could be identified by observing and closely studying the agenda setting of the posts and tweets. Moreover, the content analysis was done in several posts of the specified football journalists on various occasions, including transfers, injuries, managerial changes, criticisms and etc. Thus, this covers different football topics to help understand better professionalism, objectivity, and agenda setting in a wider range, rather than merely focusing on one aspect and leaving the rest of the football topics uncertain and undiscussed.

In the next chapter, I will look in detail at the two sports journalists chosen for study and see how framing and priming work in their cases. Social media threads are my “data”, and my “accounts”, and these will be used extensively to demonstrate how the social media conversations proceed both as images and as text.

Chapter 4

Matt and Fabrizio

In Chapter 3, I look at case study methodology and what counts as “data”, accounts-news-picture-commentaries - for this thesis. In this chapter, I look in detail at how Matt Law and Fabrizio Romano engage with social media and their audiences, in order to understand the frames involved and their consequences.

4.1 Matt and Fabrizio enter the world of social media

Picture 1: Picture of Matt Law.

Source : Telegraph

Picture 2: Picture of Fabrizio Romano.

Source : Facebook (2021a)

Fabrizio Romano posts on Facebook, too, not only on Twitter. He started using his Facebook account on 1st October 2019 by uploading a picture of himself (as shown in Picture 3) and a cover photo of him interviewing someone (as shown in Picture 4).

Picture 3: Fabrizio Romano's Facebook profile picture.

Source : Facebook (2019a)

Picture 4: Fabrizio Romano's Facebook cover photo.

Source : Facebook (2019b)

In Pictures 5 and 6, it is possible to see that, in 2020, he started posting the first two football news on two players, Davide Zappacosta and Thiago Alcantara, respectively, on the same day, without inserting any photos but only words.

Picture 5: Davide Zappacosta's transfer news update on Romano's Facebook page.

Source : Facebook (2020a)

Picture 6: Thiago Alcantara's transfer news update on Romano's Facebook page.

Source : Facebook (2020b)

Since then, he started to insert pictures of related persons when posting. On 2nd April 2023, he posted about the situation of Chelsea's head coach at that time, Graham Potter, after failing to lead the team to maintain in the top half of the English Premier League (EPL), adding a line of "should Chelsea sack Potter?" with eyes emoji (as shown in Picture 7 below). This could be interpreted as, setting an agenda for audiences to think and have opinions on this topic while not adding his own opinions to it. What's more, the use of eyes emoji can be ambiguous, yet creates an atmosphere for the audiences to have a discussion on this controversial Chelsea topic.

Picture 7: Picture of Graham Potter posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2023a)

Furthermore, he also posted about Chelsea Football Club's potential managerial changes by inserting a picture of the recently sacked German coach and Chelsea's potential coach, Julian Nagelsmann, with a smile on his face (as shown in Picture 8 below). This can be interpreted that, audiences might be led to think that Nagelsmann could be close to becoming Chelsea's coach if Potter was sacked.

Picture 8: Julian Nagelsmann's picture posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2023b)

In addition, a picture of a former Barça and current Paris Saint Germain (PSG) player, Lionel Messi, with Barça's head coach, Xavi, was posted on 31st March 2023 by Romano when giving updates on Xavi's opinion on Messi's return to Barça. However, he did not specify which is Messi and which is Xavi in the picture, but the picture just presented a person with a trophy in hand, and the other was just in a suit (as shown in Picture 9). Therefore, people who are not familiar with football might have to guess while being framed that Messi must be a great player who won trophies and has been wanted by the head coach of another team.

Picture 9: Picture of Xavi and Leo Messi posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2023c)

Moreover, in Picture 10, it is possible to see that Romano provided updates on Manchester United's striker, Marcus Rashford, on his contract extension while showing a picture of him getting appreciated by his teammates and celebrating in a match to show that he is one of the best players in Manchester United and that he is made one of their priorities for the contract extension.

Picture 10: Picture of Marcus Rashford and his teammates posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2023d)

On the other hand, it is posted by Romano that Spanish giant, FC Barcelona are not sure if their player, Ansu Fati, would definitely stay. As demonstrated in Picture 11, this post was posted attaching Ansu Fati's photo in which his facial expression doesn't show excitement.

Picture 11: Picture of Ansu Fati posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2023e)

Manchester United's head coach, Erik Ten Hag, gave updates on his opinion of wanting his players to stay in the club, which was also posted by Romano, on 31st March 2023, with a picture of Ten Hag where he was presented to look focused and serious (Picture 12).

Picture 12: Picture of Erik Ten Hag posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2023f)

These examples demonstrate that pictures play a part in agenda setting, too, leading audiences to think if the posted situation is leaning towards positive or negative without telling audiences in his own words if the situation of an incident is rather promising or hopeless. In the comment sections regarding the post, audiences are free to discuss and express their opinions, no matter if they match the post or not.

On 31st December 2021, Fabrizio Romano posted eight consecutive news on a Chelsea player, Romelu Lukaku, who is currently on loan to Inter Milan, an Italian giant, about his interviews (as shown in Pictures 13.1, 13.2, 13.3, 13.4, 13.5, 13.6, 13.7, 13.8 below).

Picture 13.1: Picture of Lukaku in an interview posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2021b)

Picture 13.2: Picture of Lukaku winning a trophy posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2021c)

Picture 13.3: Picture of Lukaku in Chelsea's shirt posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2021d)

Picture 13.4: Picture of Lukaku in Chelsea's shirt posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2021e)

Picture 13.5: Picture of Lukaku in Inter Milan's shirt posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2021f)

Picture 13.6: Picture of Lukaku posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2021g)

Picture 13.7: Picture of Lukaku posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2021h)

Picture 13.8: Picture of Lukaku posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2021i)

These posts regarding Lukaku (as shown in Picture 14.1, 14.2, 14.3, 14.4, 14.5, 14.6, 14.7 and 14.8 below) attracted discussions in the comment sections, which include their opinions towards the media and the journalist, but mostly towards the player. It was brought up that, primes are stronger if the exposure of the priming event is more frequent and will be influential on people's judgements, thoughts, and behaviour (Ewoldsen & Rhodes, 2019).

This means the frequency of reporting an event can prime audiences to have certain opinions on the event. Thus, it can be explained that most audiences had a bad impression of Lukaku because they were primed to think of that direction.

Picture 14.1: Picture of a Facebook user commenting on Lukaku related post.

Source : Facebook (2021j)

Picture 14.2: Picture of a Facebook user commenting on Lukaku related post.

Source : Facebook (2021k)

Picture 14.3: Picture of a Facebook user commenting on Lukaku related post.

Source : Facebook (2021)

Picture 14.4: Picture of a Facebook user commenting on Lukaku related post.

Source : Facebook (2021m)

Picture 14.5: Picture of a Facebook user commenting on Lukaku related post.

Source : Facebook (2021n)

Picture 14.6: Picture of a Facebook user commenting on Lukaku related post.

Source : Facebook (2021o)

Picture 14.7: Picture of a Facebook user commenting on Lukaku related post.

Source : Facebook (2021p)

Picture 14.8: Picture of a Facebook user commenting on Lukaku related post.

Source : Facebook (2021q)

The comment section of a post is influential. This is because when Facebook users go through the comment section, they can see that there are people stating their opinions or even asking people's opinions on who is the best player, who was chosen by the person in the comment section, instead of an authorised organisation or anyone professional (as shown in Picture 15 below). Later on, people would react to the particular comment, and whoever got the most reaction could be indirectly recognised as the best player. Thus, people who do not

follow football news closely or are not familiar with football might be thinking that the player who got the most reaction is undoubtedly the best player in contemporary football. In this case, it shows that there is a frame within a frame which shall be named as “comment frame”.

Picture 15: Picture of a user’s comment under a Facebook post.

Source : Facebook (2023g)

It is also similar to the case mentioned above, as shown in Pictures 16.1, 16.2, 16.3, 16.4 and thread 1 below, some users would give their opinions on who is the best player in the world, while people who disagreed would refute. Hence, it happened to have a “**defend frame**” within the “**comment frame**”.

Picture 16.1 and thread 1: Picture of Facebook users commenting in the comment section.

Picture 16.2 and thread 1: Picture of Facebook users commenting in the comment section.

Picture 16.3 and thread 1: Picture of Facebook users commenting in the comment section.

Picture 16.4 and thread 1: Picture of Facebook users commenting in the comment section.

Source : Facebook (2023h)

Scrutinising and analysing football posts posted by football journalists on social media platforms like Facebook can help identify if hidden agendas, namely framing and priming, were set or not because not all football journalists would overtly express or include their opinions in a reported topic. Rather, they could use other ways of drawing the public's attention to an event. This knowledge was efficiently gained by doing qualitative content analysis on the use of words, selection of pictures based on their facial expressions and the word's description, utilisation of emojis, the frequency of reporting the same event, the opinions of the audiences towards an event and the potential influence on the public. Through

this analysis, the unanswered existence or the disappearance of the professionalism and objectivity of a football journalist could be methodically answered. Besides analysing football posts, it is also important to closely examine football journalists' style of news presentation.

4.2 Analysis

Fabrizio Romano and Matt Law both report and give updates on football news, not only football transfer news, injuries, and managerial changes of a football club, but they, sometimes, also interact with the audience on social media. Matt Law's interactions on social media are over 2 million on Facebook (as shown in Figure 1.1) and Instagram (as shown in Figure 1.2) for the past 12 months, while Fabrizio Romano has interactions of over 40 million and 21 million on Facebook (Figure 2.1) and Instagram (Figure 2.2), respectively, for the past 12 months. As football journalists, the use of language and the selection of pictures have become two very crucial elements to lead the audience to what direction they should be thinking of a football issue, namely agenda setting.

Figure 1.1: Matt Law's interactions and posts on Facebook for the past 12 months.

Source : CrowdTangle (2023a)

Figure 1.2: Matt Law's interactions and posts on Instagram for the past 12 months.

Source : CrowdTangle (2023b)

Figure 2.1: Fabrizio Romano's interactions and posts on Facebook for the past 12 months.

Source : CrowdTangle (2023c)

Figure 2.2: Fabrizio Romano's interactions and posts on Instagram for the past 12 months.

Source : CrowdTangle (2023d)

4.2.1 Fabrizio Romano

From a priming point of view, it is suggested that the recency and the repetition of the reported news are influential in priming the audience, as the recency in priming effects states that the older the news, the less memorable it gets (Moy et al., 2016). The aforementioned Lukaku news, discussed in the case study part, demonstrates that Romano posted eight consecutive news of Lukaku. It can be analysed that he makes use of the recency of the news while taking into account the repetition of news to make priming effects as successful as possible. It is because repetition suggests that the higher frequency the news is reported, the more memorable it is to the audience (Moy et al., 2016). Thus, after all, the more recent and more frequent the same issue is reported, the more influential and useful it becomes in priming the audience.

From a framing point of view, it refers to the way a news presentation was done by a journalist in order to resonate with the current underlying scenario within the target audience group (Scheufele & Tewksbury, 2007). Therefore, it is the ways used by journalists, to draw the audience's attention to an occurring issue in football, are vital. For example, the aforementioned news of "Should Chelsea sack Potter?" with eyes emoji posted by Fabrizio Romano could be said to draw people's attention to this controversial topic after adding a line to indicate that Chelsea had lost again and had dropped out of the top half of Premier League table by adding the "mind-blown" emoji to express his disbelief in the club's recent performance (Picture 7). The use of emojis alongside words is influential because, from a semiotic point of view, it is said that words and other signs can form our perception in understanding a situation (Bignell, 2002). Besides that, the picture of Potter demonstrates that Potter's facial expression was not content after suffering another loss. It could be interpreted as Chelsea FC, a former World Champions and European Champions, should not be

performing badly as how they did this season. Therefore, Potter should be responsible for this.

As shown in the photo below, the audience who participated in the comment section started to speak out their opinions, saying that Graham Potter was nowhere near Ten Hag, Manchester United FC's coach, where 207 other users reacted or liked to show either the sarcasm or the agreement toward this statement. The next comment is that an audience thinks Chelsea's owner, Todd Boehly, had made a mistake in hiring Potter and that he should sack Potter as soon as possible. This is where gatekeeping theory comes into play, too, as it refers to not only the process of news selection but also display, shaping, channelling and others. Users are said to be participating in the gatekeeping process by forwarding and sharing content on social media, even if they do not post any content at all (Deluliis, 2015). On social media like Facebook, it is said that it is considered the performance of gatekeeping function when users consume news that is shared within their Facebook community. What is more, users would make judgements based on the bandwagon heuristic effect by thinking in the way of "I should think it that way too" when others have their thoughts on an issue, as the number of likes and reactions are the most influential elements in this aspect (Deluliis, 2015). On the other hand, on Twitter, the function "retweet", is similar to the "share" function on Facebook. It can be used to disseminate content or news to the users' Twitter community without anyone's knowledge or consent. Hence, this is how gatekeeping is done, rather than only journalists who are the gatekeepers that select news to suggest to the public what they should see (Deluliis, 2015). Thus, this proves that football journalists brought up football-related issues in their way of information selection, namely description alongside the careful selection of pictures, which lead to the discussions and interactions of the audience.

Therefore, both football journalists and the participating audience are gatekeepers on social media in disseminating news online.

Picture 7: Graham Potter's update posted by Romano with opinion-seeking frame.

Source : Facebook (2023a)

Similarly, it is reported by Romano that Manchester City's star, Erling Haaland, has been incredible by scoring 45 goals this season so far that no one would deny his achievement so far (Picture 17). He added opinions by saying, "No words left to describe this machine", and added the robot emoji to express that Haaland has been terrific and only an alien could achieve his form so far, as well as making bold the statistics of his goals.

Picture 17: Authenticity confirmation frame of Haaland's statistics post posted by Romano.

Source : Facebook (2023i)

Romano would report football news by quoting what the person involved in the issue said without adding any of his own opinions. For example, David Moyes, West Ham United FC's head coach, said that he has had enough support from the club's board while taking into account the team's recent performance (Picture 18). Moreover, Romano gives updates on players' transfer status and situation, for example, Aubameyang's transfer situation between two clubs (Picture 19). In these instances, no other comments or opinions were added by the journalist, only the facts and information were reported.

Picture 18: David Moyes' update posted by Romano with fidelity neutral frame.

Source : Facebook (2023j)

Picture 19: Pierre Aubameyang's update posted by Romano with fidelity neutral frame.

Source : Facebook (2022a)

With the examples shown above, it could be understood that there are three reporting patterns of Romano in news reporting on social media platforms, which are reporting news with a description of the particular football issue and then asking for the audience's opinions and discussions (as shown in Picture 7), disseminating news by outlining the description of the issue then adding his own opinions when the truth is indisputable (as shown in Picture 17), giving updates of a football-related issue without adding his own opinions (as shown in

Picture 18 and Picture 19). I shall have them named, respectively, as “opinions-seeking frame”, “authenticity confirmation frame”, and “fidelity neutral frame”.

4.2.2 Matt Law

On the other hand, Matt Law posted on social media, most of the time, adding his own opinions. For example, expressing his own opinions on the performance of football clubs’ managers as well as the atmosphere of Aston Villa’s stadium (as shown in Picture 20). However, in comparison to Romano’s pattern, Matt Law does not include emojis.

Picture 20: Matt Law’s opinion-expressing frame tweets.

Sources : Twitter (2023a) and Twitter (2023b)

Besides that, Matt Law, sometimes, will ask for the public’s opinions on some specific football issues and, sometimes, interact with them, just as in the examples shown below (Picture 21, Picture 22 and thread 2).

Picture 21: Matt Law’s opinion-seeking frame tweet.

Source : Twitter (2023c)

Picture 22 and thread 2: Matt Law’s opinion-seeking and opinion-expressing frame tweet and the thread.

Source : Twitter (2023d)

However, Matt Law would also report football news in a way where he does not add his own opinions but just summarises the particular football issues, as shown in Picture 23 and Picture 24. On the other hand, it is possible to see in Picture 25 that, he would also retweet others’ tweets without saying adding any comments.

Picture 23: Matt Law's fidelity neutral frame tweet.

Source : Twitter (2023e)

Picture 24: Matt Law's fidelity neutral frame tweet.

Source : Twitter (2023f)

Picture 25: Matt Law’s opinion-expressing frame retweet.

Source : Twitter (2023g)

Analysis of Matt Law’s posts shows that his football news reporting routines and patterns are “opinion-expressing frame”, “opinion-seeking frame”, and “fidelity neutral frame”.

Putting Matt Law and Fabrizio Romano’s football news reporting patterns together, it can be understood that both journalists share mutual patterns of “opinion-seeking frame” and “fidelity neutral frame”. On the other hand, Matt Law’s “opinion-expressing frame” and Fabrizio Romano’s “authenticity confirmation frame” convey information differently as the “opinion-expressing frame” tends to show, directly, the audience the journalist’s opinions on an issue, while the latter, “authenticity confirmation frame”, brings the audience to a way where they decide what to think of an issue based on the information disseminated by the journalists.

4.2.3 Understand the frames - Frames Routinisation

“**Picture frame**”, as discussed above, is a crucial but often overlooked element in framing. It plays an important role in conveying the message of the selected images and complementing the description and emojis of the post to guide the audience's interpretation. Images are a powerful way to effectively convey a message, as they can show a person's facial expression and reveal their mood to those who observe them (Goffman, 1976). Goffman suggested that there are six ways of picture representation in advertisements, they are, relative size, feminine touch, function ranking, the ritualisation of subordination, licensed withdrawal and the family (Cheatwood, 1979). Therefore, pictures are crucial because they have the ability to convey a message and speak to the audience in their own unique ways.

Fabrizio Romano posted Picture 17, which showcases Erling Haaland's exceptional football statistics. The picture features Haaland looking confident and determined, which could imply that Romano chose the photo to emphasise Haaland's outstanding performance with his statistics as a good player. In Picture 18, Romano shared updates on David Moyes's managerial position and his team's poor performance. He accompanied the update with a picture of Moyes, who appeared quite concerned. It's possible that Romano chose this particular picture to match the description and makes the post more convincing. Picture 19 shows Romano providing updates on Pierre Aubameyang's transfer status. Aubameyang appears confused in the picture as his future had not been decided yet at that moment.

“**Opinion-seeking frame**” refers to journalists who post about a footballer or a topic while adding a line asking the audience questions and their opinions towards that particular topic, just like Matt Law did in Picture 21 and Picture 22 and thread 2, where Law asks the audience if Chukwuemeka has got his chances at Chelsea and if the audience would take

Potter as a Spurs manager, in the two pictures respectively. Regarding Fabrizio Romano, he asks the fans if Potter should be asked, as shown in Picture 7.

When journalists give updates on a topic, they may apply a "**fidelity neutral frame**", which is to avoid the addition of personal opinions. For instance, in Pictures 18 and 19, posted by Fabrizio Romano, and Pictures 23 and 24, posted by Matt Law, both journalists chose to report their sources without expressing their personal views. Romano quoted the words of those involved, while Law summarised the news in the description.

Law and Romano's news presentation in opinion expressing are "**opinion-expressing frame**" and "**authenticity confirmation frame**", respectively. Law adds his own opinions when giving updates or tweeting a topic. As shown in Picture 20 and Picture 22 and thread 2, where he expresses that O'Neil and Emery are doing fantastic jobs in their clubs and Potter's Chelsea experience will be beneficial for him to bring over to the next club. Moreover, in Picture 25, the fact that Law retweeted McGrath's post implies that he has an opinion on the topic of Grealish, even though he didn't express it through words. In contrast, Romano doesn't state his opinion outright. He presents confirmed statistics of Haaland's performance, such as scoring 45 goals this season, as seen in Picture 17, to highlight his exceptional skills in European football. Romano also uses a robot emoji to indicate that Haaland's abilities surpass those of a human in football.

In summary, in this Chapter, I have demonstrated that football journalists have different patterns in producing and presenting their news. However, they will, most probably, include an "opinion-seeking frame" to ask for the audience's opinions just for the purpose of the interaction, or frame them into thinking of a particular direction. Moreover, the "fidelity

neutral frame” is installed, too, because, at the end of the day, football journalists need to provide updates on football news to the public, based merely on the facts and information they got without adding any opinions. The only way that these football journalists portray differently is through how they express their opinion, they can apply an “authenticity confirmation frame” or “opinion-expressing frame” to indirectly or directly let the audience know their opinions. However, it is up to how they want to present the news. Nevertheless, framing is included in the news presentation patterns, as the news presentations already limit and set the direction for the audience to think when consuming the news.

Chapter 5

Discussion and Conclusion

Factual reporting of sports journalism is important, indeed, essential, just as opinion commentary is important. However, the two should not be confused. Both Matt Law and Fabrizio Romano are promoted as sports journalists. As demonstrated in this thesis, Matt Law is far closer to opinion commentary than traditional sports journalism. Both have distinct approaches to conveying their opinions in football news reporting. While both use the "opinion-seeking frame" and "fidelity neutral frame," Romano also employs the "authenticity confirmation frame" as opposed to Law's use of the "opinion-expressing frame." This indicates that Law is more opinion-oriented in his reporting, often adding his own views to updates on football, whereas Romano focuses more on objective reporting, often quoting what the footballers or managers said. Journalistic professionalism is measured by objectivity. It is mentioned that "journalists should put their personal biases aside when reporting for the media" (Shah et al., 2021, p. 714). Therefore, opinion-oriented reporting can be seen as a deviation from this standard, as it involves journalists framing news and priming audiences with their own opinions. Thus, this can lead to a departure from neutrality and objectivity in news reporting. Hence, objectivity and professionalism within football journalism are impacted by agenda-setting, framing, priming and gatekeeping, which perfectly answers the second research question on whether objectivity and professionalism in football are affected by particular types of agenda-setting, framing, priming and gatekeeping.

The concepts of agenda-setting, framing, priming, and gatekeeping are influenced by the rise of social media platforms such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter. These platforms have allowed football journalists to efficiently disseminate news, closely engage with fans and

directly or indirectly encourage discussions between the audiences by sharing their opinions and starting conversations. With the convenience and popularity of social media platforms, football journalists employ various frames, they are “opinion-seeking frame”, “fidelity neutral frame”, “authenticity confirmation frame” and “opinion-expressing frame” coming from the “picture frame” alongside words as description, sometimes comes with emojis when necessary, to convey football news and draw the audience's focus towards particular subjects. This process involves football news selection and presentation by the journalists, also referred to as gatekeeping. Additionally, the interactions of other football fans, such as their comments and opinions on a topic, can have a significant impact on the opinions of certain audiences. As a result, it turns out that some news is reported frequently, which can influence the audience's opinions on those topics, which is called priming. Thus, it answers the first research question on how agenda-setting, framing, priming, and gatekeeping operate in football news within the content of social media.

Journalists aim for objectivity and professionalism when reporting the news. Objectivity involves presenting information in a neutral manner without bias or personal opinions, while professionalism aims to minimise speculation and deliver accurate news to the audience. Essentially, in other words, it is important for journalists to uphold both objectivity and professionalism simultaneously. Failing to report the news objectively would imply a loss of journalistic professionalism. Although achieving complete objectivity and professionalism may not be entirely possible, Romano, more popular than Law, strives to remain as neutral as possible in his news reporting, whereas Law tends to share his opinions and provide commentary on football news dissemination.

The two research questions of this thesis are:

RQ1) How do agenda-setting, framing, priming and gatekeeping operate in football news within the context of social media?

RQ2) Are objectivity and professionalism in football affected by particular types of agenda-setting, framing, priming and gatekeeping?

Both have been addressed in this thesis and form the basis for further research on social media platforms and their effects on journalism in general.

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